

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl arylidene thiosemicarbazones

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Abstract : 4-Tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-1-arylidene thiosemicarbazones have been synthesised by the interaction of tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl thiosemicarbazide and aryl aldehydes. These compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *P. vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, *S. typhi*, *A. niger* and *Fusarium*. The identities of these new compounds have been established on the basis of usual chemical transformations and also by UV, IR, NMR and Mass spectral analysis.

Keywords : Glucosyl isothiocyanate, thiosemicarbazide, substituted aldehydes, substituted thiosemicarbazones.

Introduction

Very few thiosemicarbazones have been reported and tested for their cytotoxic activity¹ and amoebicidal activity². In view of our interest in the synthesis of newer types of thiosemicarbazones here we report the simple method for the synthesis of substituted glucosyl thiosemicarbazones by the interaction of tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl thiosemicarbazide and aryl aldehydes. Tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl thiosemicarbazide **3** was prepared for the first time by the interaction of tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate **1** and hydrazine hydrate **2**. Required tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate **1** has been prepared by already known method³.

4-Tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-1-arylidene thiosemicarbazones **5a-e** (Scheme 1) were prepared by the interaction of tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl thiosemicarbazide **3** and aryl aldehydes **4a-e** in boiling benzene for 2 h. The product was found to be desulphurised when boiled with alkaline lead acetate solution. These compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *B. vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, *S. typhi*, *A. niger* and *Fusarium*.

Antibacterial activity : All the compounds were screened for their antibacterial activities against various

pathogenic bacteria such as *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *P. vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus*, *S. typhi*, by cup-plate method at concentration 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in DMF by using standard Co-trimazine (25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) for bacteria. Amongst the compounds tested for antibacterial activity, compounds **5a**, **5b** and **5e** showed good activity and other compounds showed moderate activity.

Antifungal activity : All the compounds were also screened for their antifungal activities by cup-plate method at a concentration at 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in DMF by using standard Griseofulvin (100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) against *A. niger* and *Fusarium*. The compounds **5a** and **5c** showed good activity against *A. niger*. While other compounds were found resistant against *Fusarium*.

Experimental

General method :

Melting points are uncorrected. Optical rotations $[\alpha]_D$ were measured on a EQUIP-TRONICS Digital Polarimeter model no. EQ 800 at 30 °C in CHCl_3 . UV spectra were recorded on a UV-Vis spectrophotometer 117 (λ_{max} 400–240 nm in benzene). IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrum RXI (4000–450 cm^{-1}) FTIR spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR were obtained on a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR) NMR spectrometer in CDCl_3

where, R = (4-5a) Phenyl; (b) (4-methoxy)phenyl; (c) (4-chloro)phenyl; (d) (4-*N,N*-dimethyl)phenyl; (e) (4-hydroxy-3-methoxy)phenyl
 Bz = Benzoyl (C₆H₅CO-)

Scheme 1

with TMS as an internal reference. The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV, and the spectra were recorded at room temperature. *m*-Nitrobenzyl alcohol (NBA) was used as matrix unless specified otherwise. Thin-layer chromatography was conducted on E. Merck TLC aluminium sheet silica Gel₆₀ F₂₅₄.

Tetra-O-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate (1): m.p. 125–126 °C (Found : C, 65.41; H, 3.96; N, 1.78; S, 4.84. Calcd. for C₃₅H₂₇O₉NS : C, 65.93; H, 4.23; N, 2.19; S, 5.02%).

Preparation of 3 :

Tetra-O-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate 1 (6.37 g, 0.01 M, 25 ml) and hydrazine hydrate 2 (0.32 g, 0.01 M) were stirred in benzene medium for 10–15 min at room temperature. The solvent was distilled off and sticky mass was isolated as residue which triturated several times with petroleum ether to give granular solid 3 (6.0 g), crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 155–157 °(d) (Found : C, 62.52; H, 4.42; N, 6.33; S, 4.81. Calcd. for C₃₅H₃₁O₉N₃S : C, 62.78; H, 4.63; N, 6.27; S, 4.78%).

Preparation of 5a-e :

Tetra-O-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl thiosemicarbazide 3, 0.003 M in benzene (15 ml) and aryl aldehydes 4a-e 0.003 M in benzene (15 ml) was heated on a boiling water bath for 2 h. After refluxing benzene was distilled off when a sticky residue obtained which was triturated with petroleum ether to afford solid 5a-e. The product

were crystallized from ethanol. The purity of the products was checked by TLC.

5a, 1.7 g (73.22%), m.p. 144–146°, [α]_D³⁰ + 47.0° (c, 0.0276 in CHCl₃); R_f, 0.70 (5 : 1; CCl₄ : EtOAc); UV (λ_{max} nm) benzene : 255.6; IR ν_{max} cm⁻¹ (CHCl₃) : 3332 (N-H), 3065 (Ar-H), 2967 (C-H, -CH₂, -CH₃), 1729 (C=O), 1602 (C=N), 1316 (C-N), 1268 (C-O), 1216 (N-C(=S)-N), 1178 (C=S), 853 (β -D-glucopyranosyl ring deformation), 711 (monosubstituted benzene ring); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 8.00–7.50 (25H, m, Ar-H), 6.01 (2H, s, N-H), 5.87–4.73 (5H, m, β -D-glucopyranosyl ring), 4.55–4.46 (2H, m, -CH₂-O-), 4.02 (1H, s, CH=N); MS (*m/z*) : 757 (M⁺), 680 (M-C₆H₅), 654 (TBG-NH-C(=S)-NH₂⁺), 579 (TBG⁺=C₃₄H₂₇O₉⁺), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found : C, 66.18; H, 4.51; N, 5.70; S, 4.45. Calcd. for C₄₂H₃₅O₉N₃S : C, 66.57; H, 4.62; N, 5.54; S, 4.22%).

5b, 1.2 g (51.06%), m.p. 140°, [α]_D³⁰ + 9.4° (c, 0.0244 in CHCl₃); R_f, 0.77 (4 : 1; CCl₄ : EtOAc); UV (λ_{max} nm) benzene : 264.5; IR ν_{max} cm⁻¹ (CHCl₃) : 3335 (N-H), 3017 (Ar-H), 2987 (C-H, -CH₂, -CH₃), 1730 (C=O), 1618 (C=N), 1313 (C-N), 1268 (C-O), 1227 (N-C(=S)-N), 1167 (C=S), 852 (β -D-glucopyranosyl ring deformation), 810 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 710 (monosubstituted benzene ring); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 8.10–7.20 (24H, m, Ar-H), 6.09 (2H, s, N-H), 5.96–4.64 (5H, m, β -D-glucopyranosyl ring), 4.60–4.40 (2H, m, -CH₂-O-), 4.12 (1H, s, CH=N), 3.71 (3H, s, CH₃-O); MS (*m/z*) : 787 (M⁺), 680 (M-C₆H₄-*p*-OCH₃), 654 (TBG-NH-C(=S)-NH₂⁺), 579 (TBG⁺=C₃₄H₂₇O₉⁺), 120 (CH₂=C₆H₃-*p*-O-CH₃⁺), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found :

C, 65.44; H, 4.60; N, 5.19; S, 4.25. Calcd. for $C_{43}H_{37}O_{10}N_3S$: C, 65.56; H, 4.70; N, 5.33; S, 4.06%.

5c, 1.9 g (80.50%), m.p. 158–160°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 22.0^\circ$ (c, 0.0238 in $CHCl_3$); R_f , 0.66 (5 : 1; CCl_4 : EtOAc); UV (λ_{max} nm) benzene : 326.4; IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} ($CHCl_3$) : 3330 (N-H), 3066, 3019 (Ar-H), 2952 (C-H, -CH₂, -CH₃), 1728 (C=O), 1601 (C=N), 1316 (C-N), 1269 (C-O), 1216 (N-C(=S)-N), 1178 (C=S), 852 (β -D-glucopyranosyl ring deformation), 826 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 711 (monosubstituted benzene ring), 686 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 8.10–7.26 (24H, m, Ar-H), 5.99 (2H, s, N-H), 5.67–4.61 (5H, m, β -D-glucopyranosyl ring), 4.52–4.46 (2H, m, -CH₂-O-), 4.06 (1H, s, CH=N); MS (m/z) : 792 (M+1), 791 (M⁺), 668 (TBG-NH-C(=S)-NH=NH⁺), 579 (TBG⁺=C₃₄H₂₇O₉⁺), 551 (TBG-CO), 475 (TBG-C₆H₄CO), 214 (Cl-*p*-C₆H₄-CH=N-NH-C(=S)-NH₂⁺), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found : C, 63.95; H, 4.11; N, 4.89; S, 4.38; Cl, 4.13. Calcd. for $C_{43}H_{34}O_9N_3S$: C, 63.71; H, 4.29; N, 5.30; S, 4.04; Cl, 4.48%).

5d, 1.7 g (71.12%), m.p. 118–120°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 8.6^\circ$ (c, 0.0112 in $CHCl_3$); R_f , 0.30 (4 : 1; CCl_4 : EtOAc); UV (λ_{max} nm) benzene : 297.5; IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} ($CHCl_3$) : 3331 (N-H), 3022 (Ar-H), 2953 (C-H, -CH₂, -CH₃), 1729 (C=O), 1605 (C=N), 1316 (C-N), 1268 (C-O), 1215 (N-C(=S)-N), 1178 (C=S), 853 (β -D-glucopyranosyl ring deformation), 818 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 711 (monosubstituted benzene ring); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 8.07–7.17 (24H, m, Ar-H), 6.04 (2H, s, N-H), 5.91–4.72 (5H, m, β -D-glucopyranosyl ring), 4.50–4.39 (2H, m, -CH₂-O-), 3.99 (1H, s, CH=N), 3.52 (6H, s, -N(CH₃)₂); MS (m/z) : 800 (M⁺), 756 (M-N-(CH₃)₂), 680 (M-C₆H₄-*p*-N(CH₃)₂), 654 (TBG-NH-C(=S)-NH₂⁺), 579 (TBG⁺=C₃₄H₂₇O₉⁺), 475 (TBG-C₆H₄CO), 222 ((CH₃)₂N-*p*-C₆H₄-CH=N-NH-C(=S)-NH₂⁺), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found : C, 65.62; H, 5.01; N, 6.86; S,

4.14. Calcd. for $C_{44}H_{40}O_9N_4S$: C, 66.00; H, 5.00; N, 7.00; S, 4.00%).

5e, 2.0 g (83.33%), m.p. 108–110°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 23.6^\circ$ (c, 0.0124 in $CHCl_3$); R_f , 0.90 (5 : 1; CCl_4 : EtOAc); UV (λ_{max} nm) benzene : 247.2; IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} ($CHCl_3$) : 3555 (O-H), 3342 (N-H), 3019 (Ar-H), 2976 (C-H, -CH₂, -CH₃), 1728 (C=O), 1602 (C=N), 1316 (C-N), 1269 (C-O), 1215 (N-C(=S)-N), 1178 (C=S), 1054 (1,3,5-trisubstituted benzene ring), 852 (β -D-glucopyranosyl ring deformation), 711 (monosubstituted benzene ring); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 8.10–7.03 (23H, m, Ar-H), 6.96–6.93 (1H, b, O-H), 5.98 (2H, s, N-H), 5.97–4.62 (5H, m, β -D-glucopyranosyl ring), 4.44–4.36 (2H, m, -CH₂-O-), 4.10 (1H, s, CH=N), 3.97 (3H, s, CH₃-O); MS (m/z) : 804 (M+1), 803 (M⁺), 684 (M-C₇H₃O₂), 655 (TBG-NH-C(SH)-NH₂⁺), 604 (TBG-NC⁺), 579 (TBG⁺=C₃₄H₂₇O₉⁺), 475 (TBG-C₆H₄CO), 209 (HO-*p*-C₆H₃-*m*-OCH₃)-CH=N-NH-C=S⁺), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found : C, 64.01; H, 4.25; N, 4.90; S, 4.17. Calcd. for $C_{43}H_{37}O_{11}N_3S$: C, 64.25; H, 4.60; N, 5.23; S, 3.98%).

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